

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 3
Microphotographs of thinsections of
pebbles and cobbles from
Lower Jurassic conglomerates

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Poorly sorted quartz arenite, 15-v15-25/12

Poorly sorted lithic arenite, 15-v15-25/10

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